

Outdoor Activities to Discover Medians and Centroid of Triangles

Maria Antonietta Lepellere and Dario Gasparo

University of Udine, Middle School “G. Caprini” Trieste

The article describes the steps that led students to the discovery of properties of triangles and to the construction of medians, perpendicular bisectors (axes), and notable points. The approach used is that of Inquiry and Embodied cognition in outdoor context. The activity involved 15 students from a middle school in Trieste, Italy. The results were tested by proposing to the same students five types of exercises on axes, medians, heights and bisectors and the notable points connected to them. Success rates were averaged and divided between those that were subjected to outdoor activities (axis and median) compared to those that were carried out in the classroom (heights and bisectors). A further comparison was made between the success rates in drawing the objects under investigation. Finally, we investigated through Mentimeter the students’ appreciation of the outdoor activity. 100% of students found the activity fun and helpful and the 85% of them considered group work to be useful.

Introduction

We are in a pandemic era, the need to move is even more important, like that of being together, collaborating, asking, and solving problems, breathing outdoors. Italy has had an extraordinary history of open-air public schools that began in the early 1900s for weak, fragile children who risked contracting TB (D’Ascenzo, 2018). After some experience it was noticed that these students learned more and better than the others, so they were also extended to “normal” children. The experience continued even during fascism. After the war it resumed strongly and ended in 1977 in Imola (Bo), when the last outdoor school closed, under the pressure of full-time and declining enrolments. In 2016, the “National Network of Outdoor Schools” was established in Italy, which groups and harmonizes the different experiences of a structured outdoor school system, where lessons outside the classroom can be taught, promoting students to rediscover a relationship with nature. More than 53 institutes currently belong to it. In the early 1900s, the outdoor school movement was widespread in many countries (Germany, England, France, Spain, United States, etc.) too. Recently there has been an increased interest in the development of outdoor and adventure education programmes (Fägerstam & Samuelsson, 2012). It would be an opportunity to use the virus catastrophe to change schools using the good practices of the past that have a lot to say even in the “digital” era. Never like now adolescents and young people need a true relationship with the teacher, to take responsibility, to learn from experimentation, to do manual and artistic work.

The purpose of this article is twofold: it is intended to show how an outdoor activity should be presented with a view to the Embodiment, the Inquiry and with the aim of facilitating peer collaboration; to test whether outdoor activities have been effective for understanding concepts and whether they have been appreciated by students. The activity presented involved 15 students from a middle school in Trieste, Italy.

Theoretical Background

Learning outside the classroom essentially can be defined as use of resources out of the classroom to achieve the goals and objectives of learning (Knapp, 2010; Smith & Walkington, 2020). The constant focus on textbooks and formal mathematical practice might invoke a view among students that mathematics is abstract, distanced and only useful in a classroom context. Existing research on outdoor learning in mathematics indicates positive affective outcomes and possible academic benefits from learning mathematics in an out-of-school context (Daher & Baya'a, 2012; Moffett, 2011). Moreover, outdoor environments are real-life contexts enabling children to internalise, transfer and apply mathematical ideas and provide direct experience, the students need to be active in the learning process (Moffett, 2011). It lends itself to the Inquiry-based mathematics education, a student-centered form of teaching whose guiding principle is that the students are supposed to work in ways like how professional mathematicians work (Artigue & Blomhøj, 2013; Dorier & Maass, 2014): they must observe phenomena, ask questions, look for mathematical and scientific ways of answer these questions, interpret, and evaluate their solutions, and communicate and discuss their solutions effectively. Cooperative learning gives the opportunity to discuss and reason with others and justify one's mathematical thoughts on how to solve different mathematical problems. Cooperative outdoor learning in mathematics gives the possibility to observe that a task at hand can be solved in more than one way and that more than one "right" solution to the problem may exist. The sensorimotor experiences arising from the environment also play a paramount role in learning (Wilson, 2002).

Embodied cognition is described as a bodily sense of knowing, expressed through physical movement and sensory exploration with environments (Kim et al., 2010; Merleau-Ponty, 2002; Smith & Gasser, 2005; Varela et al., 1991). There is complexity in the processes that may be involved in the development of embodied cognition as "knowledge depends on being in a world that is inseparable from our bodies, our language, our social history" (Varela et al., 1991, p. 173). According to Glenberg (2010) perception and how memory works is affected by how people move their bodies. To that vein, Hu, Ginns et al. (2015) suggested that pointing and tracing gestures might enhance geometry learning by activating an "increased working memory channel". The role of gestures as semiotic tools, contributing to deeper understanding of mathematical concepts (Arzarello et al., 2009).

Learning geometry can foster the ability to think logically, develop problem solving ability and reasoning, and can support many other topics in mathematics (Duval, 1995; Fischbein, 1993; Mariotti, 1995). According to Carden & Cline (2015) visualization refers to mental processes that describe visual or spatial information. Furthermore, for Arcavi (2003), visualization is a process that is the result of the creation, interpretation, reflection of images, diagrams with the aim of describing and communicating information on the development of an idea that is not known in advance to obtain a higher understanding.

The Methodology

In the first part we describe those steps that led students to the discovery of properties regarding triangles, to the construction of median, perpendicular bisectors (axis) and notable points. The approach used is that of Inquiry and Embodied cognition in an outdoor context. The activity takes place in the “Classroom under the sky” (for other activities see https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lGJbz_d7OU&t=80s). The environment is already welcoming in itself: a small pond right on the edge of a laurel grove, an open lawn that converges to the maple tree in the centre of the space, under which a blackboard and seats for students are placed. The students can also make use of portable shelves, to support books and notebooks. The activity involved 15, six grade students, 4 boys and 11 girls, from a middle school in Trieste, Italy. Students were randomly divided into 4 groups of 4/5. The results were tested by proposing, to the same 15 students, 5 types of exercises, one of these about drawing, on axes, medians (which were taught outside the classroom), heights and bisectors (which were taught in the classroom), and the notable points connected to them. Success rates were averaged and divided those that were subjected to outdoor activities compared to those that were carried out in the classroom. Finally, we investigated through Mentimeter the students’ appreciation of the outdoor activity.

The Activities

The activities regard the discovery of the rules of drawing, those rules that lead hand and body to trace elements that take position on the surface of the lawn, with established criteria and simple tools, ancestors of the modern squares and compasses that crowd our school desks. Ropes, broomsticks, wooden stakes are our tools and some plastic caps. The square is the same one used by the ancient Egyptians 5 thousand years ago: 1 piece of rope divided, by means of knots, into 12 equal pieces. A short video of the activity carried out can be found at: tinyurl.com/outdoortriangles.

The Perpendicular Line and the Axis

The activity starts by asking the kids to build a triangle by giving them 3 pieces of wooden planks deliberately of inappropriate lengths: they must find out why it is not possible. They discover, after several attempts, the fundamental property: The sum of the lengths of any two sides of a triangle is always greater than the length of the third one.

After building whatever triangles they wish, each group is asked to identify the midpoint of each side of the triangle. One group uses a piece of rope as a unit to measure one side and then calculates the half, another group uses a rope to measure one side, it joins the two extremes obtained to have the half.

At this point some teacher's suggestion is needed, students don't know yet certain techniques (Figure 1). By fixing one end of the string to the vertex of the triangle (A), a sufficiently wide arc is drawn (2), so it is possible to identify all the points that are at the same distance from that vertex: we call it an arc of circumference. We move to vertex (B), belonging to the same side, repeating operation (3) thus identifying two crossing points of the

arcs which are both at the same distance from the ends of 4 and 5. By joining these two points, a straight line is drawn, which marks its midpoint (M) on the side. Now it is their turn: the students understand that they must position themselves on the vertices of the triangle, so crouched on the ground, bent on the knees, they hold down the vertex of competence with their fingers on the ground. Another member of the group hands one end of the rope to the partner who holds it on the vertex. After leaving the vertex, as there are no other classmates to help, a student identifies another point on the rope so that the distance from the first extreme is greater than half of the side, which is done by estimating the position of the midpoint. He lowers himself, grasps this end of the string between index, thumb, and middle finger and, with some difficulty, also binds the plaster to proceed with the formation of the bow. At the suggestion of the teacher, he forms a loop on the string and inserts the chalk into it to be freer in movement. At this point, with the back bent but in an upright position, the pupil draws an arc: his task is to keep the rope always in tension, so that the radius remains constant. Some students suspect that these axes form right angles to the side. Three students take the knots of our piece of rope divided into 12 equal pieces every 3, 4 and 5 segments and stretch it to obtain a right triangle. The impression is confirmed by positioning our large right-angled triangle of rope with the right angle placed on the identified midpoint (M). It is really true! The traced segment passes through the midpoint of the side perpendicularly. It is now up to the teacher to propose a name for this remarkable line: the axis.

Figure 1

The Axis

The Circumcenter and the Circumference Circumscribed

We note that in all the triangles of the groups the three axes cross in a single point. But “obtuse triangle group” has a strange design: did they do something wrong? Their point lies outside the triangle, on the longest side, the one opposite the obtuse angle. They explain how they proceeded, and the “acute triangle groups” confirm that the classmates followed the correct procedure. The peer review is a fundamental aspect in mathematics: it favors collaboration, the exchange of ideas and critical observation. It is precisely by leveraging on collaboration that students can build theorems themselves and then have the satisfaction that the theorem will not take the name of some important mathematician but will be reported in the notebook with the acronym of their names. Let us go back to the obtuse triangle and the axis. The only thing that has changed compared to the other “experiments” is precisely the

shape of the triangle, so we can argue that in the obtuse triangles the point of intersection of the axis ends outside the triangle. It is time to give a name to this center-point: we call it Circumcenter. At this point the students are invited to look for another characteristic. In the right triangle, the crossing point is neither “inside” nor “outside”, but it is “up”: it is in fact on one side; the longer one, facing the right angle.

They are asked to discover other particularities: some suspect that the distances from the vertices to the circumcenter may matter. Here the circle comes into play, which although not treated in the 6th grade, always arouses its charm. The end of the rope is now fixed on the circumcenter while another student stretches the rope until it reaches a vertex. He holds the end between his forefinger and thumb and checks that by rotating around the triangle by 360° it touches all the vertices. The circumference is circumscribed and therefore the point is called circumcenter.

The Centroid

We continue to take advantage of the fact that we have already identified the midpoints of the sides to discover another notable point: the centroid. What could be done with the midpoints of the three sides of the triangle? Some propose to unite them among themselves, others to unite them at opposite vertices. Both hypotheses are verified. Finally, the students join each vertex of the triangle to the midpoint of the opposite side: all these segments cross in a single point, *O* (Figure 2). The name of a geometric part is almost never accidental: since it arrives at the midpoint of the side, these segments are called medians. The meeting point is called centroid and it is the centre of gravity.

Figure 2

The Centroid

Once again, the challenge of identifying properties starts. The students soon discover that this point divides each median into two parts such that the one containing the vertex is longer than the other. Invited to measure them, the students discover that the first part is exactly double the other.

The Test

The next day a test containing 5 exercises was administered to attest the knowledge learned on axis and medians experienced outdoors as well as in classroom, but also height and bisectors learned only in class. Exercise 1. “Keywords table”: Write an “X” in the cell where there is a characteristic that serves to define the notable segment of the triangle (height,

median, bisector or axis). Exercise 2. “Definitions”: Define: The bisector is ... The height is ... The median is ... The axis is ... Exercise 3. “Characteristics”: Report at least one characteristic of each segment and each notable point of the triangle: Medians ... Bisectors ... Axis ... Exercise 4. “Notable points”: Fill in the table indicating in which triangles the notable points are internal (write “int”), external (write “ext”) or lie on one side or a vertex (write “up”). Exercise 5. “Drawing”: Draw the required parts on the triangles, identify the crossing point; when you can, draw the inscribed or circumscribed circumference.

Results

Table 1. shows the averages of the success rates on all 5 exercises that concerned axis and medians (first row), topics addressed outdoors as well as in the classroom, with the same ones on heights and bisectors (second row). The differences of the previous percentages have been added in the third row.

Table 1

Success rate

	Success rate														
Axis & Median	73	61	39	54	35	80	93	73	61	79	68	73	13	35	70
Height & Bisector	63	45	25	31	25	82	92	19	43	41	47	44	0	30	65
Differences	10	16	13	23	10	-1	1	54	18	37	21	29	13	6	5

We immediately notice a significantly higher score of the exercises on the topics covered outdoors, axis and medians, with respect to height and bisectors treated in the classroom. Only for a student with an excellent success rate, the results are comparable: correct answers “outdoors” 80%, “indoors” 82%. For five of the other 15 students, the outdoor activity resulted in an advantage of more than 20%. In outdoor activities, the results are also more homogeneous: a percentage change coefficient of 50% for axis and 60% for medians with respect to 103% for heights and 99% for bisectors. The difference between outdoor and indoor activities (see Table 2) is even more evident for Exercise 5 on drawing: the average success rate is for outdoor activity equal to 75% (axis) and 70% (median) while for indoor activity 38% (heights) and 41% (bisectors).

Table 2

Exercise 5: Success rate

	Success rate of Exercise 5 on Drawing														
Axis & Median	100	60	35	23	50	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	40	55	100
Height & Bisector	90	53	23	20	0	100	100	13	23	23	53	23	0	13	100
Differences	10	7	12	3	50	0	0	87	77	77	47	77	40	42	0

Finally, we wanted to investigate through Mentimeter the students’ appreciation of the outdoor activity. The students were asked to write the first 5 words that came to mind when they think about the outdoor activity. The results are summarized in Figure 3 below (on the left) together with the same request made the next day in the light of the previous answers (on

the right). In both cases the expression “funny / fun” was the most voted followed by “collaboration / working with and in group / group / being together”.

Figure 3

Mentimeter

Conclusions

Covid-19 launches a challenge to schools today in a strong crisis and that of outdoor schools is a real way that connects students with reality, nature, dexterity, art and a new responsibility towards creation, others, themselves. The reduction of opportunities for socialization has led to various psychological disorders in adolescents: panic attacks and anxiety. It should therefore come as no surprise that fun and socializing activities are of interest and approval. The survey carried out anonymously at the end of the outdoor lesson shows that 100% of students found the activity fun. Several used terms such as “beautiful, joy, happiness”. 85% of students considered group work to be formative and useful, and the words “interesting, formative, learning” were reported by almost all students. Test results have also always been to the advantage of outdoor activity.

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